

University College Dublin

School of Mechanical & Materials Engineering

< MEEN3005W-Mechanics of Fluids 2 >

*Research on The Thermal Model of Electric Vehicle
Battery Packs Based on Air-Cooled Heat Dissipation*

Group Number: Group 18

Group information and CRedit

Name	UCD Number	CHU Number	Work
Shile Zhang	23219317	2023902778	Experiments, data collection
Lingtong Meng	23219311	2023902129	Simulation and visualization
Lianghao Zhang	23219540	2023901554	Modelling and analysis
Shuoqi Lai	23219353	2023901865	Poster design and visualization

Directed by: Dr.Muhammad Sajid

& Dr.Xuehui Wang

1 Introduction

Global energy consumption has increased sharply in recent decades, and this growth has been accompanied by worsening environmental degradation. Energy shortages and pollution have therefore become two major challenges facing the world today. Among the many contributing sectors, transportation plays a particularly important role. In the United States, for example, the transportation sector consumed approximately 70% of petroleum in 2017 and accounted for about 10% of carbon dioxide emissions. Against this background, electric vehicles have attracted increasing attention as a practical approach to reducing fuel consumption and lowering emissions. Their high energy efficiency and zero tailpipe emissions make them especially promising. The performance of electric vehicles, however, depends heavily on the battery system. Lithium-ion batteries are now widely used for this purpose because they offer several advantages over lead-acid and nickel-metal hydride batteries. They are smaller and lighter, yet provide higher energy density, stronger power output, better charging efficiency, longer cycle life, lower self-discharge, and no memory effect.

Temperature is one of the key factors affecting the performance, durability, and safety of lithium-ion batteries. At low temperatures, electrochemical reaction rates decrease, which reduces available capacity and weakens battery performance. High temperatures create a different problem. They accelerate battery ageing and, under severe conditions, may lead to thermal runaway. For this reason, an effective battery thermal management system is essential for maintaining stable and safe operation. Several cooling methods have been developed, including liquid cooling and phase change material cooling. These approaches generally provide good thermal performance, but they also tend to involve more complex structures, higher cost, and greater maintenance requirements. Air cooling, by contrast, is simpler, safer, lighter, less expensive, reliable, and easier to maintain. Based on these advantages, this report focuses on the design of an air-cooling system for lithium-ion batteries.

2 Related works

How best to maintain lithium-ion batteries within a moderate operating temperature range and to minimize thermal gradients across battery packs are a major questions of battery thermal management system (BTMS) research. Existing literature generally splits along three lines: cooling medium selection, structural configuration, and thermal control variables. The report reviewed here span all three areas, and Table 1 summarizes them by primary focus.

A. Cooling Media

Most BTMS research centers on air, liquid coolant, or phase change materials (PCMs). Air remains widely used because of its low cost and lightweight structure, but its limited heat capacity becomes a bottleneck under high-rate charge and discharge scenarios. Liquid coolant provides higher heat removal capability and can maintain battery temperatures more effectively. Nevertheless, the penalty is hardware, including flow channels, cooling plates, pumps, and reliable sealing structures, which increase system complexity and introduce reliability concerns. PCMs take a different approach. Instead of carrying thermal energy away, they store it as latent heat during phase transitions, which tends to even out temperature across the pack. Once the material is completely melted, however, its buffering effect rapidly diminishes. Furthermore, most PCMs also conduct heat poorly, thus slowing heat dissipation and delaying thermal recovery following intensive thermal events.

B. Structure

The physical configuration of a BTMS is largely determined by the selected cooling medium. Air-cooled systems are the simplest, generally built on ducts and fans to push airflow over cell surfaces. Liquid-cooled systems are commonly designed around cooling plates and mini-channels. PCM-based systems even go further, wrapping cells with phase-change layers and incorporating embedded cooling plates to improve conductive heat transfer.

Optimizing these structural layouts has received considered attention. For instance, Wang et al. rearranged the inlet and outlet positions of an air-cooled system, and added parallel plates to redistribute airflow, which improves temperature uniformity across the pack. Results like these are encouraging, yet such structural refinements are often

accompanied by trade-offs that are not fully considered. More sophisticated geometries also increase mass and complicates maintenance. These additional costs can easily be overlooked when thermal performance is the sole metric being optimized.

C. Controlled Variable

The controlled variables manipulated in BTMS study fall broadly into two camps: geometric ones and flow-related ones. Geometric optimization typically involves adjustments to battery arrangement, channel configuration, or PCM thickness, whereas flow-related studies mainly regulate parameters such as airflow rate, coolant flow rate, and flow direction. In practice, the boundary between them is often less clear, since changing a channel dimension inevitably reshapes the flow field too. Zhao et al. and Yang et al. offer typical examples in liquid- and air-cooled systems, where design parameters were tuned to reduce peak battery temperature.

The thing less widely recognized is that even studies described as “active control” strategies usually amounts to flow regulation rather than direct thermal intervention. Wang and Ma’s reciprocating-airflow strategy is a useful case. They switched airflow patterns in a large prismatic battery pack, achieving more uniform cell-to-cell temperature. However, the controlled variable was still the airflow distribution pattern, rather than the inlet-air temperature itself. This distinction matters, because a control strategy based entirely on flow regulation without direct temperature feedback, may provide limited adaptability under varying thermal conditions.

D. Summary

The studies reviewed above follow on a familiar recipe: pair cooling media with refined geometry, and tune flow-related parameters until thermal performance is improved. Although these approaches can improve heat dissipation and temperature uniformity, the associated cost and complexity are hard to ignore. Additional components not only increase system mass and volume, but also complicates packaging design and maintenance.

How performance is assessed is an important limitation as well. Surface temperature and cell-to-cell temperature are the common metrics, but core temperature, which can deviate substantially from the surface under heavy load conditions, is seldom modelled or measured.

The control methodology has a similar blind spot. The controlled variables are flow-related parameters in most air-cooled studies, whereas temperature is only treated as a monitored output rather than a direct control input. Consequently, the control strategy responds indirectly through airflow regulation rather than directly to thermal state.

This report takes a different approach to investigate a simplified duct-and-fan air-cooled BTMS. An electrothermal coupling model is employed to estimate both surface and core temperatures, enabling the control strategy to respond directly to the actual thermal condition of the battery.

Table 1 Comparison of representative BTMS studies

Author	Cooling media	Structure	Controlled variable
Yang, W., et al.	Air and liquid	Mini-channel and fan	Geometry and flow
Zhao, L., et al.	Air and liquid	Jacket and fan	Geometry and flow
Ding, B., et al.	Liquid and PCM	PCM layer and cooling plate	Flow
Singh, L. K., et al.	Air and PCM	PCM layer and fan	Geometry and flow
Wang, M., et al.	Air	Air duct and fan	Geometry
Wang, H., & Ma	Air	Air duct and fan	Flow
Tao, X., & Wagner, J.	Air	Air duct and A/C	Temperature
Guo, R., & Li, L.	Liquid	Cooling plate	Geometry and flow
Weng, J., et al.	PCM	PCM layer	Geometry
This work	Air	Air duct and fan	Temperature

3 Battery thermal model

3.1 Equivalent Circuit Model of The Battery

Considering both model accuracy and computational complexity, this paper adopts a second-order RC network equivalent circuit model, as shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 The circuit model of the battery

R_s refers to the internal resistance of the battery, representing the total internal resistance. R_1 , R_2 and C_1 , C_2 form a circuit consisting of two RC branches in series. The two capacitors C_1 and C_2 simulate different energy storage processes within the battery, while the resistors R_1 and R_2 describe current losses during different discharge stages. V_1 and V_2 are the voltages across the two RC branches, respectively. V_T is the terminal voltage, which is also the output voltage of the battery. V_{OCV} represents the open circuit voltage.

Based on Kirchoff's laws, the equations can be established as below

$$I = C_1 \frac{dV_1}{dt} + \frac{V_1}{R_1}$$

$$I = C_2 \frac{dV_2}{dt} + \frac{V_2}{R_2}$$

$$V_T = V_{OCV}(SOC) - V_1 - V_2 - IR_s$$

Based on the Bernardi formula, the heat produced by the battery can be represented as

$$Q = Q_r + Q_j + Q_{\text{phase-change}} + Q_{\text{mixing}}$$

where Q_r represents the electrochemical reaction heat in the battery, Q_j represents the Joule heat, Q_{mixing} represents the mixing heat generated by concentration gradients, $Q_{\text{phase-change}}$ represents the heat generated in the process of phase changing. Joule heat is the main heat source inside the battery. Therefore, Q can be simplified as:

$$Q = Q_j = I(V_{OCV} - V_T) - IT_b \frac{dV_{OCV}}{dT_b} = I^2 R - IT_b \frac{dV_{OCV}}{dT_b}$$

In this equation, T_b refers to the temperature of the battery, R is the internal resistance of battery, in which the Ohmic and polarization internal resistance are both involved, $\frac{dV_{OCV}}{dT_b}$ is the temperature coefficient of battery, which is denoted as λ_1 .

When the temperature of battery decreases, the solubility of electrolytes also decreases, thus:

$$R = \lambda_2 T_b + \lambda_3$$

The λ_2 and λ_3 are the fitting coefficients. Therefore, the expression of Q can be obtained:

$$Q = I^2(\lambda_2 T_b + \lambda_3) - IT_b \lambda_1 = (-\lambda_1 I + \lambda_2 I^2) T_b + \lambda_3 I^2$$

3.2 Heat-Transfer Model of The Battery

The axial thermal resistance of the battery is small, so the axial temperature transfer can be neglected. Therefore, the battery is equivalently divided into two parts: the inner core and the surface, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The diagram of the battery heat transfer model

The heat transfer coefficient between the battery and air is:

$$h = \frac{Nu \cdot k_a}{D} = 0.27 \left(\frac{\rho_a D}{\mu} \cdot \frac{L}{L-D} \right)^{0.63} Pr^{0.36} (Pr/Pr_w)^{0.25} \frac{k_a}{D} \cdot v^{0.63}$$

Let:

$$\lambda_4 = 0.27 \left(\frac{\rho_a D}{\mu} \cdot \frac{L}{L-D} \right)^{0.63} Pr^{0.36} (Pr/Pr_w)^{0.25} \frac{k_a}{D}$$

Due to the range of temperature change is limited, ρ_a , μ , Pr , Pr_w and k_a can be considered as constants. Thus, the heat transfer coefficient is a function of air speed v . Therefore, the convection heat dissipation can be expressed as (T_a is the temperature of air, A_b is the area of battery):

$$Q_{conv} = \lambda_4 A_b (T_b - T_a)$$

According to existing studies, the thermal model of each battery is given by the following equations, denote:

$$f_1(v) = \frac{n\lambda_4^2 A_b^2 \cdot T_{b,1}}{2\rho_a c_a S_a \cdot v^{0.37} + n\lambda_4 A_b}$$

$$f_2(v) = \frac{2\rho_a c_a S_a \lambda_4 A_b \cdot v}{2\rho_a c_a S_a \cdot v^{0.37} + n\lambda_4 A_b}$$

$$f_3(v) = \frac{2\rho_a c_a S_a \lambda_4 A_b \cdot v - n\lambda_4^2 A_b^2 \cdot v^{0.63}}{2\rho_a c_a S_a \cdot v^{0.37} + n\lambda_4 A_b}$$

$$\dot{T}_{b,n} = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{(-\lambda_1 I + \lambda_2 I^2) - \lambda_4 A_b v^{0.63}}{c_b m_b} T_{b,1} + \frac{\lambda_3 I^2 + \lambda_4 A_b T_a v^{0.63}}{c_b m_b} \right], n = 1 \\ \frac{f_1(v)}{c_b m_b} T_{b,1} + \frac{(-\lambda_1 I + \lambda_2 I^2) - f_2(v)}{c_b m_b} T_{b,n} + \frac{\lambda_3 I^2 + f_3(v)}{c_b m_b} T_a, n > 1 \end{cases}$$

In these equations, $\dot{T}_{b,n}$ is the temperature change of n-th battery, T_a is the air temperature at the inlet. The value of parameters in thermal model is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 The value of parameters in thermal model

Objective	Parameter	Value	Unit
Battery cell	D	0.026	m
	A_b	5.309×10^{-3}	m ²
	m_b	0.073	kg
	c_b	1120.97	J/(kg·K)
	$\frac{dV_{OCV}}{dT_b}$	-0.3×10^{-3}	V/K
Air	ρ_a	1.185	kg/m ³
	c_a	1005	J/(kg·K)
	k_a	0.0263	W/(m·K)
	μ	1.835×10^{-5}	kg/(m·s)
	Pr	0.702	/
	Pr_w	0.7	/
	T_a	298	K
Fundamental condition	L	0.035	m
	S_a	2.275×10^{-3}	m ²

4 CFD simulation

We performed geometric modeling and meshing of the battery pack using the preprocessing software SpaceClaim, resulting in a battery pack with air-cooled heat dissipation, as shown in the Figure. The battery selected

for this study is a cylindrical A123-26650 LiFePO4 cell with a diameter D of 26 mm and a center-to-center spacing L of 35 mm between cells. The cells are arranged in parallel, with air flowing in from the left and out from the right.

Figure 3 Meshing diagram of the battery pack

Next, configure the battery pack in FLUENT. In the Domain Types section, the model is divided into two parts: the internal heat source and the air domain. Set the internal heat source type to SOLID and the air domain type to FLUID, and define the material properties as shown in Table 3. For boundary types, considering that the battery pack relies on airflow for cooling, set the inlet type to VELOCITY_INLET and the outlet type to PRESSURE_OUTLET; set the top and bottom boundary types to SYMMETRY; and set the battery surface type to WALL.

Table 3 Battery and air attribute parameters

Parameter	Battery Core	Air
Density[kg/m ³]	2007.98	1.185
Specific Heat[J/(kg·K)]	1120.97	1005
Thermal Conductivity[W/(m·K)]	19.03	0.0263

Since the heat generation rate of each battery varies depending on factors such as internal resistance, airflow velocity, and the battery's own temperature, and since each battery has a different heat generation rate, we use a UDF function to customize the battery heat source. The configuration interface is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Setting energy source and velocity

The time step is set to 1 s, the number of time steps to 1,800, and the maximum number of iterations per time step to 20. The simulation results show the operating conditions of the battery pack when the inlet air temperature is 25 °C, the initial battery temperature is 25 °C, and the initial inlet air velocities are 1 m/s, 2 m/s, and 3 m/s, respectively. The battery temperature and streamline map shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Temperature and streamline distribution ($v=1$ m/s)

5 Reliability analysis

Figure 7 shows the comparison between the model and simulation in different setup (i.e., (a) $v=1$ m/s, $I=4.6$ A; (b) $v=2$ m/s, $I=4.6$ A, (c) $v=3$ m/s, $I=4.6$ A; (d) $v=1$ m/s, $I=9.2$ A; (e) $v=2$ m/s, $I=9.2$ A; (f) $v=2$ m/s, $I=9.2$ A.), in which the maximum error is lower than 0.6 °C. Thus, the reliability of simulation can be proved.

Figure 7 Comparison between the model and simulation temperature

Reference

- [1] G. Zhao, X. Wang, M. Negnevitsky, H. Zhang, "A review of air-cooling battery thermal management systems for electric and hybrid electric vehicles," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 501, 230001, 2021.
- [2] L.K. Singh, R. Kumar, A.K. Gupta, A.K. Sharma, S. Panchal, "Computational study on hybrid air-PCM cooling inside lithium-ion battery packs with varying number of cells," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 67, 107649, 2023.
- [3] R. Guo, L. Li, "Heat dissipation analysis and optimization of lithium-ion batteries with a novel parallel-spiral serpentine channel liquid cooling plate," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 189, 122706, 2022.
- [4] B. Ding, Z.-H. Qi, C.-S. Mao, L. Gong, X.-L. Liu, "Numerical investigation on cooling performance of PCM/cooling plate hybrid system for power battery with variable discharging conditions," *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, vol. 141, pp. 625–633, 2020.
- [5] X. Tao, J. Wagner, "A thermal management system for the battery pack of a hybrid electric vehicle: modeling and control," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part D: Journal of Automobile Engineering*, vol. 230, no. 2, pp. 190–201, 2016.
- [6] W. Yang, F. Zhou, H. Zhou, Q. Wang, J. Kong, "Thermal performance of cylindrical lithium-ion battery thermal management system integrated with mini-channel liquid cooling and air cooling," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 175, 115331, 2020.
- [7] H. Wang, L. Ma, "Thermal management of a large prismatic battery pack based on reciprocating flow and active control," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 115, pp. 296–303, 2017.
- [8] M. Wang, S. Teng, H. Xi, Y. Li, "Cooling performance optimization of air-cooled battery thermal management system," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 195, 117242, 2021.
- [9] J. Weng, X. Yang, G. Zhang, D. Ouyang, M. Chen, J. Wang, "Optimization of the detailed factors in a phase-change-material module for battery thermal management," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 138, pp. 126–134, 2019.
- [10] L. Zhao, W. Li, G. Wang, W. Cheng, M. Chen, "A novel thermal management system for lithium-ion battery modules combining direct liquid-cooling with forced air-cooling," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 232, 120992, 2023.